

Physico-chemical, computational, antibacterial and DNA cleavage studies of (*E*)-*N*¹-[(3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxyl methyl)-2-methyl pyridine 4-yl)methylene]aceto hydrazone hydrochloride and its copper complex

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Abstract : In an attempt to understand the properties of compounds with potent anti-tumor and metal chelator properties, the structural aspects of (*E*)-*N*¹-[(3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxyl methyl)-2-methyl pyridine 4-yl)methylene]aceto hydrazone hydrochloride (HHMPPMAH) were studied by various spectral techniques. To understand chelation properties of the same compound, its Cu^{II} complex was synthesized and characterized by employing various spectro-analytical tools viz. Mass, IR, UV-Vis, TGA, ESR, magnetic measurements, SEM and EDX. The pH-metric titrations with title compound carried out at constant temperature 303 K and 0.1 M KNO₃ ionic strength inferred number of dissociable protons in it and further studies with spectrophotometric technique employing Job's continuous variation method enabled in establishing the composition of its Cu^{II} complex. Further DNA cleavage and biological activity studies against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria in present investigation are informative to throw an insight for future scheming of *in vitro*, *in vivo* studies. Hyper Chem 7.5 tools were employed to compute the contour maps of frontier orbitals, binding energies, QSAR and molecular parameters. The contour maps of electrostatic potentials for both ionic and molecular forms of title hydrazone were computed to envisage the donor properties.

Keywords : HHMPPMAH, Cu^{II}-HHMPPMAH complex, Hyper Chem 7.5, TGA, SEM, EDX, ESR, antibacterial, DNA cleavage.

Introduction

The analogues of pyridoxal isonicotinoyl hydrazone (PIH) have been currently used to treat iron overload in the treatment of cancer as well as controlling tumour growth¹. Literature survey reveals high efficiency of these compounds over desferrioxamine (DFO) for iron binding²⁻¹³. They exist predominantly in neutral state at physiological pH allowing easy access across cell membranes into intracellular iron pools¹⁴. The analogues of PIH are known to possess good protection against convulsions¹⁵ including iron chelation. Keeping in view the biological significance of PIH, in the present investigation we intended to study the extensive properties of (*E*)-*N*¹-[(3-

hydroxy-5-(hydroxyl methyl)-2-methyl pyridine 4-yl)methylene]aceto hydrazone hydrochloride (HHMPPMAH) (Fig. 1). The title compound HHMPPMAH was synthesized and its structural properties were studied by Mass, IR, NMR and UV-Vis spectral studies. Equilibrium studies employing pH-metry and spectrophotometry were carried out to elucidate its ligation properties. Further its copper complex was synthesized and characterized by Mass, IR, UV-Visible, SEM and EDX, TGA, ESR and magnetic data to establish geometrical and electronic properties. DNA cleavage studies as well as antibacterial activity were also explored to ensure the potential of both title ligand and its copper

Fig. 1. (*E*)-*N*¹-[(3-Hydroxy-5-(hydroxyl methyl)-2-methyl pyridine 4-yl) methylene] aceto hydrazone hydrochloride (HHMMPMAH).

complex to establish further route for advanced biological investigations. To understand the frontier molecular orbitals and their energies computational studies were carried out by employing Hyper Chem 7.5 tools.

Materials and methods :

Chemicals :

All the chemicals used are AR grade. Pyridoxal hydrochloride is procured from Sigma Aldrich, hydrazine hydrate and methyl acetate from Merck and copper chloride from SD's fine chemicals. The organic solvents used were obtained as pure grade materials.

Instrumentation :

The purity of compound was ascertained by recording LC-MS data on Shimadzu LC-MS 2010A in negative mode. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 435 spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker WH (270 MHz) spectrometer. UV-Visible spectrum was scanned on UV-3600 Shimadzu spectrophotometer. The pH measurements were made using a digital Elico electronic model LI 120 pH meter using Irving-Rossotti pH titration technique¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Spectrophotometric measurements were performed on a UV-1700 Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer by employing Job's continuous-variation method¹⁹. Mass of the Cu^{II}-HHMMPMAH complex was recorded on VG AUTOSPEC and the magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Faraday balance model 7550. The morphology, size and elemental composition of title compound and its Cu^{II}-HHMMPMAH complex were examined using Ziess scanning electron microscope (SEM)^{20,21} coupled with an energy dispersive X-ray system (INCA EDX). Thermo gravimetric (TGA)²²⁻²⁴ and differential thermal analyses

(DTA) of complex were carried out on Shimadzu TGA-50 H in the temperature range 0–1000 °C. The ESR²⁵ spectrum was recorded on BRUKER-EMX using X-band radiation.

Synthesis :

The title compound (*E*)-*N*¹-[(3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxyl methyl)-2-methyl pyridine 4-yl)methylene] aceto hydrazone hydrochloride (HHMMPMAH) (Fig. 1) was synthesized by reported method²⁶. The Cu^{II} complex was synthesized refluxing a mixture of title compound HHMMPMAH (0.005 mole) and anhydrous CuCl₂ (0.005 mole) in methanol medium on water bath for 10–12 h by adjusting pH in the range 6.0–7.0 to enable complex formation. The precipitated solid complex was filtered off, washed with water, hot ethanol and petroleum ether. The product was dried in air and stored in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂ under vacuum.

DNA cleavage studies :

The DNA cleavage studies were carried out using Agarose gel electrophoresis. The DNA cleavage analysis potency of the compound and its copper complex were quantitatively evaluated on super coiled plasmid pBR322 in the absence of oxidizing or reducing agents.

Antibacterial studies :

The antibacterial activity of the title compound and its copper complex was studied by applying the disc diffusion method²⁷ for determining the degree of sensitivity of microbes to antibiotics. The compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus* (Gram-positive) and *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gram-negative) bacteria.

Computational tools :

The molecular modelling program Hyper Chem 7.5 was employed for computational studies. The geometry optimization of built molecular structure of HHMMPMAH was done with the semi-empirical PM3 method²⁸. The properties of frontier orbitals, electrostatic potential were envisaged from contour maps generated at single point calculation. The QSAR data useful to define physico-chemical descriptors is computed for optimized structure.

Results and discussion

Spectro-analytical and computational studies of HHMPPMAH :

Mass :

LC chromatogram of the compound showed a single peak at 0.828 min. The Mass spectrum of HHMPPMAH displayed peaks at m/z 222, 258 corresponding to $[M-H]^+$ and $[M+HCl-1]^+$ ions respectively.

IR :

IR spectrum exhibited a broad band in the range of 3300–3400 cm^{-1} attributable to phenolic OH and aliphatic OH stretching vibrations. The band at 3180 cm^{-1} corresponds to (ν_{N-H}) stretching vibrations. The other stretching frequencies were recorded at 1656 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{C=O}$), 1562 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{C=N}$) and 1134 cm^{-1} (ν_{C-O}). The appearance of shoulder and broad nature of the band above 3000 cm^{-1} indicate extensive inter and intra molecular hydrogen bonding²⁹.

NMR :

The ^1H NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 showed peaks at δ 12.5 (OH, s, aromatic), 11.5 (1H, s, NH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 8.1 (1H, s, aromatic), 5.6 (OH, s, aliphatic), 4.63 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.6 (3H, s, CH_3 , acetyl) and 2.2 ppm (3H, s, CH_3). Phenolic OH, aliphatic OH and NH protons readily exchanged with D_2O . The ^{13}C NMR spec-

trum (Fig. 2) of title compound recorded in DMSO- d_6 , displayed signals at δ 167 and 150 ppm corresponding to azomethine carbon and carbonyl (C=O) carbon. The peaks at δ 147, 144, 135, 132, 124 ppm are attributable to aromatic ring carbons, aliphatic carbons at δ 58, 21 and 18 ppm correspond to methylene carbon, methyl carbon of N-acetyl group and methyl carbon attached to ring respectively.

UV :

The electronic spectrum of HHMPPMAH recorded in dilute acetic acid (1 : 1) showed absorption maxima at wavelengths λ of 293 nm (34129 cm^{-1}) and 340 nm (29411 cm^{-1}). These peaks may be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{C}=\text{N})$ transitions respectively.

Equilibrium studies :

The chelation properties of the title compound were studied by Irving-Rossotti titration technique at constant temperature 303 K in 70% v/v ethanol-water medium and 0.1 M KNO_3 ionic strength (Fig. 3). The proton dissociation constants were calculated from linear plots of $\log(2 - \bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A - 1)$, $\log(1 - \bar{n}_A)/\bar{n}_A$ vs pH, where \bar{n}_A is average number of protons associated with ligand (Figs. 4 and 5). The results revealed that the pK_{a1} value at 4.40 corresponds to ring NH^+ and pK_{a2} at 8.86 to phenolic proton.

Fig. 2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of HHMPPMAH.

Fig. 3. pH titration curves of HHMPPMAH system in 70% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at 303 K and 0.1 M ionic strength.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log (2 - \bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A - 1)$ vs pH of HHMPPMAH system in 70% (v/v) ethanol-water medium.

Fig. 5. Plot of $\log (1 - \bar{n}_A)/\bar{n}_A$ vs pH of HHMPPMAH system in 70% (v/v) ethanol-water medium.

The results from spectrophotometric technique applying Job's method of continuous variation (Fig. 6) signify the formation of 1 : 1 [M : L] metal complex at 420 nm wavelength.

Characterization of metal complexes of Cu^{II}-HHMPPMAH complex :

Mass :

In the mass spectrum of Cu^{II}-HHMPPMAH base peak observed at m/z 396 [M+2]⁺ is ascribable to 1 : 1 [M : L] composition of metal complex. The other peaks displayed in the spectrum correspond to adduct ions.

Fig. 6. Plot of absorbance versus mole fraction of HHMPPMAH at 30 °C in dilute acetic acid (1 : 1) medium.

IR :

The IR spectrum of the Cu^{II}-HHMPPMAH complex displayed a band at 3365 cm⁻¹ which corresponds to coordinated water, where as an absorption due to OH group is absent in the complex spectrum when compared to ligand spectrum. The shift in vibration bands observed from 1562 to 1458 cm⁻¹ (C=N) and 1134 to 1093 cm⁻¹ (C-O) in the complex spectrum are attributable to the participation of imine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen in coordination with metal ion respectively. The additional bands observed in the spectrum of complex corresponds to M-Cl, M-N and M-O stretching in the range of 400 to 650 cm⁻¹ is evident for the complex formation.

UV-Visible :

The electronic spectrum of Cu^{II}-HHMMPMAH (Fig. 7) recorded in DMSO displayed absorption bands in the UV region at 300 nm (33,333 cm⁻¹) and 350 nm (28,571 cm⁻¹) indicate $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (C=O), $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ of (C=N) transitions. Shift in absorption bands to higher wavelength and an absorption band observed in visible region at 420 nm (23,809 cm⁻¹) in the complex spectrum attributable to d-d transitions evident for complex formation.

Thermo gravimetric analysis :

Thermo gravimetric analysis of Cu^{II}-HHMMPMAH indicated weight loss in two steps. In the first step the

weight loss in the range of 150 to 250 °C and the gradual weight loss in the second step from 250 to 450 °C correspond to loss of coordinated water and decomposition of ligand moiety around the metal ion. The residue remaining above 1000 °C corresponds to metal percentage there by indicating 1 : 1 composition of the complex. Three exothermic peaks at 214 °C, 244 °C and 356 °C in DTA curve of the complex are probably due to decomposition of ligand, signifying the presence of more number of nitrogen atoms which can provoke explosive nature.

ESR studies and magnetic properties :

The X-band ESR spectrum of copper complex recorded at room temperature (Fig. 8) indicated a single peak at

Fig. 7. UV-Vis spectrum of Cu^{II}-HHMMPMAH complex.

Fig. 8. ESR spectrum of Cu^{II}-HHMMPMAH complex.

3342G with average 'g' value 2.082 pronouncing less anisotropy. The magnetic moment of 1.98 BM calculated from magnetic susceptibility measurements is in accordance with electronic properties of complex. From all the spectral investigations and results of solution chemistry, tentatively the structure (Fig. 9) for the Cu^{II} complex of HHMPPMAH is predicted.

Fig. 9. Tentative structure of Cu^{II}-HHMPPMAH complex.

SEM and EDX :

SEM image of HHMPPMAH and its copper complex (Fig. 10a and 10b) displayed different morphologies. The former appeared as rock like structure with the particle size 200 μm while the latter as thin cotton fibers with the particle size in the range of 100 μm. EDX spectrum of complex (Fig. 11a and 11b) recorded the presence of chlorine along with copper including carbon, nitrogen and oxygen substantiating the formation of copper complex. The results obtained are in good agreement with mass

Fig. 10. SEM images of (a) HHMPPMAH, (b) Cu^{II}-HHMPPMAH complex.

Fig. 11. EDX spectrum of (a) HHMPPMAH, (b) Cu^{II}-HHMPPMAH complex.

spectral data and in support of 1 : 1 composition of the complex.

DNA cleavage studies :

The DNA cleavage studies (Fig. 12) were carried out on the title compound and its Cu^{II} complex. The results reveal that Cu^{II} complex was found to be an efficient DNA cleaver which has converted DNA from Super coiled form (SC) (form I) into Nicked circular form (NC) (form II). It is interesting to understand from the results that the title compound in bound form with metal ion exhibited such cleavage activity but not free uncoordinated compound throwing prominence on the importance of metal complexes interaction with DNA.

Computational studies :

The molecule of the title compound was optimized

Fig. 12. DNA cleavage activity of ligand and its Cu^{II} complex.

(Fig. 13a and 13b) both in molecular and ionized forms using the Hyper Chem 7.5 tools for computing the data pertinent to molecular orbitals and also to explore molecular properties. The frontier molecular orbitals viz. highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMO)³⁰ of the chemical species are important to predict their reactivity^{31,32}. The energy gap between HOMO-LUMO orbitals for molecular form (Fig. 14a and 14b) as well as for ionic form (Fig. 15a, 15b) was calculated using semi empirical PM3 method. As the observed binding energy value of title compound for HOMO in ionized form is relatively low compared to its molecular form, it can be presumed that ionized form is more suitable for complex formation with

Fig. 13. Geometry optimized structure of (a) molecular form, (b) ionized form of HHMPPMAH.

Fig. 14. Binding energy of (a) Highest Occupied Molecular Orbitals (HOMO), (b) Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbitals (LUMO) in molecular form.

Fig. 15. Binding energy of (a) Highest Occupied Molecular Orbitals (HOMO), (b) Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbitals (LUMO) in ionic form.

metal ion. The contour maps of electrostatic potentials (Fig. 16a and 16b) of both molecular and ionic forms signifying the negative electrostatic potential regions may envisage that phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen are only suitable sites to bind with metal ion³² to form a stable six membered chelating ring with the metal ion. The QSAR parameters (Table 1) like surface area, hydration energy, log *P* (*P* – Partition coefficient), refractivity, polarizability, mass and molecular properties viz. dipole moment and RMS gradient were determined. These properties focus a variety of molecular properties and related structural properties of compound with their physico-chemical features and biological activities.

Fig. 16. Electrostatic potential of HHMPPMAH in (a) molecular form, (b) ionized form.

Table 1. QSAR and molecular properties of HHMPPMAH

QSAR properties :	
Surface area (Approx.)	366.66 Å ²
Surface area (Grid)	430.93 Å ²
Volume	672.84 Å ³
Hydration energy	-12.36 kcal/mole
log <i>P</i>	-0.47
Refractivity	54.14 Å ³
Polarizability	22.54 Å ³
Mass	223.23 amu
Molecular properties :	
Total energy	-63469.82 kcal/mole
Dipole moment	7.409 Debyes
RMS Gradient	0.09924 kcal/Å mol

Antibacterial studies :

The comparison of biological activity with different strains of bacteria revealed that the HHMPPMAH under investigation is highly active against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria except with *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Table 2), and its activity is relatively high against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* compared to Ampicillin standard. While copper complex of HHMPPMAH exhibited high activity with *Bacillus cereus* and moderate activity with all other organisms.

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of HHMPPMAH and its Cu^{II} complex

Name of the bacteria	Ligand activity	Cu ^{II} complex activity	Ampicillin activity
Gram-positive :			
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	35±0.4	15±0.4	32±0.1
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	15±0.5	19±0.5	24±0.2
Gram-negative :			
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	35±0.8	14±0.6	17±0.1
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	22±0.5	7±0.5	17±0.1
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	NA	8±0.5	18±0.2
+ <20 mm (slightly active), ++ <30 mm (moderately active), +++ >30 mm (highly active).			

Conclusion

The physico-chemical properties studied are informative in understanding structural and ligational properties of HHMPPMAH. The computational studies carried out

enabled to understand electrostatic potential, QSAR and molecular properties of title compound. Spectro analytical data obtained for copper complex is useful to establish its electronic and geometrical properties. Equilibrium studies carried out by using pH-metric and spectrophotometric techniques comprehend the potential donor sites in title compound and stoichiometry of its complex. The results of antibacterial and DNA cleavage studies are useful for planning further advanced biological studies.

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Eshwari *et al.* : Physico-chemical, computational, antibacterial and DNA cleavage studies *etc.*

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